

Coated wire ion selective electrodes for determination of cationic and anionic surfactants

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Abstract : In this paper two new coated wire ion selective electrodes are reported, one of which, prepared by aliquot permanganate as electroactive material, found to be useful for the determination of cationic surfactants. The other one, which was prepared using the ion-pair complex formed between cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and sodium dodecylsulfate (SDS) was found to be useful for the determination of anionic surfactants. Dip coating technique was used for the preparation of these electrodes. The characteristics of electrodes in terms of electrode response, response time, and working range of pH have been evaluated.

Keywords : Coated wire ion selective electrodes, cationic surfactants, anionic surfactants, surfactant selective electrodes.

Introduction

Surfactants as environmental pollutants are present in various samples, including natural and waste water¹. Spectrophotometry and titration techniques are often used for the determination of different surfactants²⁻⁶. Ion selective electrodes have also been used for the determination of surfactants⁷⁻⁹. In this paper two new coated wire ion selective electrodes are reported, one of which is designed for the determination of cationic surfactants and the other is sensitive towards anionic surfactants.

Results and discussion

Electrode response :

The response of electrode-I was evaluated by taking different concentrations of the cationic surfactant, CTAB and by recording the millivolt (mV) values for each solution using the electrode-I as indicator electrode and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. A fairly linear response in the concentration range $1 \times 10^{-1} - 5 \times 10^{-5} M$ was observed (Fig. 1). A number of solutions of the anionic surfactant, sodium dodecylsulfate (SDS) were prepared in the concentration range of $1 \times 10^{-1} - 1 \times 10^{-6} M$ and the response of each solution was recorded using electrode-II as indicator electrode and a saturated

calomel electrode as reference electrode. A fairly linear range of electrode response was observed in the concentration range $1 \times 10^{-1} - 5 \times 10^{-6} M$ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Response curves for electrode-I (◆) and electrode-II (■).

Response time :

The response time of both electrodes was determined by measuring the response of the respective electrode at the interval of 5 s. It was observed that the response time for electrode-I and -II are 25 s and 20 s respectively (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Response time for electrode-I (♦) and electrode-II (■)

Effect of pH :

In order to study the effect of pH on electrode response, a number of solutions were prepared with a fixed concentration ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) of cationic and anionic surfactants and varying the pH of these solutions in the range 1 to 12. The potential of the series of solutions prepared from CTAB were measured with electrode-I and a saturated calomel electrode. It was observed that the response remains unchanged in the pH range 4–10 (Fig. 3). Similarly a series of solutions of anionic surfactant, SDS were prepared in the pH range 1 to 12. The response of each solution was measured with electrode-II. It was observed that in the pH range 3–10, the response remains constant (Fig. 3).

The above mentioned characteristics for both the electrodes are summarized in Table 1, which reveals that both the electrodes have excellent detection limits and longer working pH range with comparatively small response time.

Fig. 3. pH Response for electrode-I (♦) and electrode-II (■).

Table 1. Characteristics of surfactant ion selective coated wire electrode

Electrode	Slope of response curve	Detection limit (M)	Working pH range	Response time (s)
I	62	1×10^{-1} – 5×10^{-5}	4–10	25
II	59	1×10^{-1} – 5×10^{-5}	3–10	20

Experimental

Materials and apparatus :

Analytical reagent grade sodium dodecylsulfate ($C_{12}H_{22}SO_4Na^+$, SDS, Fluka) and cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, Fluka) were used without any purification. Aliquot 336 (Lancaster), potassium permanganate ($KMnO_4$, Glaxo Laboratories), benzene (Qualigens Excelar), polyvinyl chloride (PVC) (Sigma), tetrahydrofuran (BDH) and ethanol (Bengal Chemicals and Pharmaceuticals Ltd.) were used as received. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. A century (CP 901) pH meter with a saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode was used. All measurements were made at 30 ± 1 °C.

Methods :

Preparation of electrode-I :

0.5 g of potassium permanganate was dissolved in water and 0.5 g of Aliquot 336 was dissolved in 5 mL of benzene. Both solutions were poured into a separatory funnel. After shaking, the organic phase which contained aliquot permanganate was separated off as electroactive material. 0.2 g of polyvinyl chloride was dissolved in 7

to 8 mL tetrahydrofuran, and then this solution was mixed in 1 : 1 ratios by volume with solution containing the electroactive material. To this solution, a co-axial copper wire was dipped several times to obtain a bead at the end of the wire which was then air dried¹⁰.

Preparation of electrode-II :

Ion-pair cetyl trimethylammonium-dodecylsulphate (CTA-DS) was prepared by dropwise addition of 10 mL of a hot (50 °C) aqueous solution (0.05 M) of sodium dodecylsulfate to 30 mL of a hot ethanol-water mixture (volume ratio = 2 : 1) containing equimolar amount of cetyl trimethylammonium bromide.

The reaction mixture was heated and stirred at 68 °C. By further heating up to 80 °C, a white precipitate was formed. The mixture was stirred at 80 °C until all the ethanol was evaporated. After cooling, ion-pair CTA-DS was filtered off and washed thoroughly with distilled water repeatedly in order to ensure complete removal of bromide ion. The isolated precipitate was dried at 80 °C until constant weight and stored in desiccator. To a solution, prepared by dissolving 0.3 g of polyvinylchloride in 5 mL tetrahydrofuran, 0.5 g CTA-DS precipitate was added. It was stirred till a homogenous solution was obtained. By dip coating of co-axial wire, the electrode was prepared.

The entire cell assembly, involving these coated wire type electrodes could be represented as :

Metal | Ion selective membrane | Sample solution | External Reference Electrode

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